

FAN, TA'LIM, TEXNOLOGIYA VA ISHLAB CHIQRARISH INTEGRATSIYASI ASOSIDA RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI NOMLI III ILMYI ONLAYN KONFERENSIYA

AI Assistance and Its Advantages in Language Learning

Asia International University

English Language teacher

Mustafoeva Durdoni Ilyosovna

Asia International University

Student of the group 6 FT (i) 24

Ganiyeva Madinabonu Narzullo qizi

Abstract

The great advancement of technology has made its impact on every sphere of our lives and education is an outstanding example of this modification. Artificial intelligence possesses a great influence in terms of language learning offering the chances of personalized approach and many other merits which are analyzed in this very article.

Keywords

Artificial intelligence, administrative processes, proficiency level, traditional methods, personalized approach, constructive feedback, to mitigate anxiety

Introduction

According to the definition provided by McCarthy (2007) Artificial Intelligence (AI) is the ability of machines to imitate the intelligence of human behavior which can be in the form of intelligent computer programs. Its role in the field of education is rapidly increasing since it can guarantee an improvement in teaching methods and handling with administrative processes. Teaching English as a Second Language is the scope where AI has paramount impact on. The tools depending on artificial intelligence are being utilized to offer more enjoyable atmosphere and immediate feedback. The advantages of it grow bigger when its appropriateness for all ages and proficiency levels is taken into consideration. However, these very advancements are not without potential hazardous effects.

Challenges of language learning

Learning a new language is very demanding work, especially when students only have an access to traditional methods of learning. These very methods are only dependant on textbooks, audio recordings lacking personalized approach to the learner. Even though teachers' presence is included in the process it elevates the

FAN, TA'LIM, TEXNOLOGIYA VA ISHLAB CHIQRISH INTEGRATSIYASI ASOSIDA RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI NOMLI III ILMYI ONLAYN KONFERENSIYA

level of anxiety that students experience. Speaking in front of other students goes beyond that. AI assisted tools can be demonstrated as a solution to these issues because of their characteristics enabling students to utilize them in privacy at the pace suitable for their needs. The emergence and development of AI to revolutionize the traditional methods of teaching caused an attention from the members of educational field ([Michalski et al., 2013](#)).

Advantages of AI assisted tools in language learning process

There is no doubt about the ways how AI can modify the educational field by offering the following merits:

1. Personalized learning.

It provides students with personalized approach as it evaluates their strength and weakness and creates lesson plans creating their very needs which mean that they can be exposed to the language at their own pace (Maher, J. 2023).

2. Real-time feedback

Apps assisting the language learning process are able to analyze the speech of the students, recognize their mistakes and advise the ways of improving their skills.

3. Anywhere and anytime access to learning

The role of this advantage grows even bigger with regard to the population who has a limited access to take advantages of traditional class opportunities.

4. Making the learning process more engaging

Most AI assisted technological tools use games to engage their learners in the process making it more fun. Competitive feature of it enabling students to see what other students are achieving also comes from this advantage.

5. Alleviated anxiety

As Zhong (2024) claims learners are described as stepping out of their comfort zone and practicing their language without a fear of being judged as AI's assistance in providing constructive feedback in a non-judgmental way has an ability of mitigating anxiety.

Conclusion

It can be speculated that the future of learning language is highly dependent on the role of AI. It can be employed in the aforementioned sphere as a tool to enhance the language learning process for all ages and the learners of different proficiency levels since it has many benefits in the form of providing immediate feedback, personalized learning opportunity, flexibility, lowering anxiety level and making the learning process more engaging.

FAN, TA'LIM, TEXNOLOGIYA VA ISHLAB CHIQRARISH INTEGRATSIYASI ASOSIDA RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI NOMLI III ILMIY ONLAYN KONFERENSIYA

Reference

Maher, J. (2023). *Personalized Learning through AI*.

McCarthy, J. (2007). *From here to human level- AI*.

[Michalski et al., \(2013\)](#). *Machine Learning. An Artificial Intelligence Approach*.

Zhong, W. (2024). *The therapeutic effectiveness of artificial intelligence-based chatbots in alleviation of depressive and anxiety symptoms in short-course treatments: A systematic review and meta-analysis*.